

Review of statistical water temperature models for a Peruvian Andean river (Supplementary Material)

Efrain Noa-Yarasca¹, Diana Chaca Ayuque², Hugo A. Galvan Ccora², Ivan A. Ayala Bizarro²,
Ada Arancibia³.

¹Oregon State University, Corvallis, OR 97331, EEUU.

²National University of Huancavelica, Huancavelica 09001, Perú.

³National University of Engineering, Lima 15333, Perú.

Correspondence to: Efrain Noa-Yarasca (enoay7@yahoo.com)

1. Supplementary material S1

Table S1. Calibrated parameters for Ichu River flow in the SWAT model

Código del parámetro	Descripción	Valor ajustado
CN2.mgt	Número de curva	x 1.29
ALPHA_BF.gw	Factor alfa de flujo base (días)	0.23
GWQMN.gw	Profundidad de umbral de agua en el acuífero poco profundo necesaria para que se produzca el flujo de retorno (mm).	1.85
ESCO.hru	Factor de compensación de la evaporación del suelo.	0.82
CH_N2.rte	Valor n de Manning para el canal principal.	0.14
CH_K2.rte	Conductividad hidráulica efectiva en aluviones del canal principal. (mm/hr).	118.4
SOL_K1.sol	Conductividad hidráulica saturada (mm/hr).	X 1.72

Figure S1. Flow calibration of the Ichu River at the Huancavelica station

2. Supplementary material S2

Convergence of statistical model equation coefficients for water temperature prediction using the Latin Hypercube Sampling method.

Linear equation of Stefan & Preud'homme.

Figure S2. Convergence of coefficient 'a'

Figure S3. Convergence of coefficient 'b'

Non-linear Mohseni & Stefan equation of 3 parameters.

Figure S4. Convergence of coefficient α .

Figure S5. Convergence of coefficient β .

Figure S6. Convergence of coefficient γ .

Non-linear Mohseni & Stefan equation of 4 parameters.

Figure S7. Convergence of coefficient α .

Figure S8. Convergence of coefficient β .

Figure S9. Convergence of coefficient γ .

Figure S10. Convergence of coefficient μ .

3. Supplementary material S2. Performance of the modified Mohseni & Stefan model for the Ichu River.

Figure S11. Performance of the modified nonlinear model of Mohseni & Stefan of 3P in the Ichu River stream temperature simulation

Figure S12. Performance of the modified nonlinear model of Mohseni & Stefan of 4P in the Ichu River stream temperature simulation